

Analysis of Community Empowerment Governance through Social Entrepreneurship Programs in DKI Jakarta Province

Yuhendra¹, Isbandi Rukminto Adi², Ety Rahayu²

¹Social Welfare Doctoral Student, University of Indonesia

²Lecturer of Social Welfare, University of Indonesia

ABSTRACT : Poverty assuagement is not only accomplished with a strategy to reduce the expenditure burden of the poor and vulnerable with help of social protection programs (Social Assistance and Social Security), but simultaneously with a strategy to increase income with help of the Social Entrepreneurship Program. This research aims to describe and analyze the governance of social entrepreneurship programs. Research data are collected from investigations through observations, interviews, and documentation research with research subjects Beneficiary Families (KPM) of the Family Hope Program (PKH) who have graduated in DKI Jakarta Province. The research approach used is qualitative with the type of explanatory research. The results show that there are four governance that influence the success of social entrepreneurship programs in poverty assuagement, they are: the program planning process for mapping and analyzing problems in determining program intervention policies for KPM, the pre-production process to identify needs that affect the development of the KPM business, the production process includes business training and division of tasks according to their expertise, as well as post-production processes to identify business development and marketing.

KEYWORDS -Poverty, Empowerments, Governance, Social Entrepreneurship

I.INTRODUCTION

Poverty has become a global issue that is quite complicated and has become a concern for all countries, specifically poor and developing countries. Poverty is a condition of not meeting the basic needs of a decent life and inadequate facilities and infrastructure [1]. Poverty exists in light of the fact that there are gaps in numerous forms that place a person, family, group, and/or state in a situation that does not have the ability to develop itself in accomplishing multiple functions that are proper for life and humanity. The poverty condition of a country or region reflects the level of welfare of the population living in that country or region [2].

Indonesia as a developing country is still encountered with the issue of poverty that does not have the ability to be overlooked. The Central Statistics Agency (BPS) released the number of poor people in Indonesia in March 2022 reaching 26.2 million people with a poverty rate of 9.54 percent. This number has decreased by 0.17 points compared to September 2021. Nevertheless, the poverty targets in the 2015-2019 National Medium-Term Development Plan (RPJMN) and 2020-2024 RPJMN have never been achieved.

Figure 1. Targets and Realization of Poverty Levels in Indonesia.

*poverty rate target by 2024. (Source: BPS 2021, RPJMN 2015-2019, RPJMN 2020-2024).

Based on the figure above, the realization of the poverty rate in Indonesia during the observation period reached an average of 10.03 percent with fluctuating growth. The achievement of the realization of the poverty rates every year has never reached the RPJMN target. Referring to the latest realization of the poverty rate, March 2022 is still 3.55-2.55 percent adrift to achieve the poverty rate target of 6.0-7.0 percent in 2024. Poverty policies or intervention assuagement are needed to achieve the target in 2024, considering that the average difference in poverty reduction is only 0.23 points per year.

Poverty assuagement endeavours are explicitly guaranteed in the 1945 Constitution, such as promoting the general welfare, educating the nation's life, and realizing a just and prosperous society. The central government and local governments continue to strive to develop poverty assuagement policy strategies aimed at reducing the burden of expenditure and increasing the income of the poor and vulnerable through comprehensive social protection policies (RPJMN 2020-2024). Comprehensive social protection aims to empower the Indonesian population to achieve a decent level of welfare and be capable to overcome socio-economic liability through cash transfer programs and social insurance. Comprehensive social protection is implemented by the integration of numerous poverty assuagement programs in a synergistic and integrated manner [3].

ADB [4] defines social protection as a set of policies and programs that are intentionally designed to reduce poverty and vulnerability, with intervention strategies in the form of promoting efficient labour markets, reducing risks, and increasing the capacity to protect against threats and upheavals such as loss of income. Whilst, according to the World Bank (2014), social protection is defined as an effort that focuses more on prevention, which includes social security, investment in human resources, and expediencies to overcome social inequality. One form of social protection program that is widely adopted by developing countries in the world is Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT).

Budlender [5] defines CCT as a conditional cash transfer program to the poor and vulnerable with the aim of increasing income and assisting individuals and households in overcoming numerous issues of devastations, risks, and crises. As a strategic policy, the CCT program is implemented in the Family Hope Program (PKH). PKH was introduced as a policy to encourage families to access health and education services, thereby strengthening the quality of a country's workforce in the future.

In its implementation, the CCT program has significantly improved human resource development. Nonetheless, it has not helped families to be independent in terms of livelihood [6]. This is consistent with other evidence showing that cash transfers alone do not have the ability to overcome the structural barriers to sustainable employment and livelihoods faced by the poor and vulnerable [7]. Numerous research results show that in general, the conditional cash transfer program as a policy for poverty reduction has not produced noteworthy results. Poverty reduction as a result of program interventions is only superficial, and unsustainable, and does not encourage an increase in beneficiary independence. In this case, empowerment policy interventions are needed to optimize community participation in achieving sustainable social welfare improvements. Community participation endeavours are accomplished through family and community empowerment programs.

Payne [8] further argues that empowerment is essentially aimed at helping people gain the power to make decisions and determine actions to be taken related to self-development, including reducing the effects of

personal and social barriers in taking action. This is done through increasing the ability and self-confidence to use the available power, among others, through the transfer of power from the environment.

The basic principle of empowerment aims to help the poor and vulnerable in building the social functioning of individuals, groups, and communities. One of the programs that empower poor communities and families is implemented through social entrepreneurship. Hulgard [9] stated that social entrepreneurship is “*social entrepreneurship can be defined as the creation of social value that is produced in collaboration with people and organizations from the civil society who are engaged in social innovations that usually imply and economic activity*”. Based on the definition, there are four dimensions of social entrepreneurship, including: first, social value, such as creating social benefits for the community and the surrounding environment. Second, civil society, specifically community initiatives and participation by optimizing social capital in the community. Third, Innovation, which is presenting social innovations that come from local wisdom. Fourth, is economic activity, namely the existence of economic activities that support social missions.

Perrini and Vurro[10], and Austin et al. [11] stated that social issues are one of the causes of poverty, and one way to overcome them is through empowerment programs through entrepreneurship. Social value creation and innovation are one of the business models or economic activities, hence, to support these activities, skills, business opportunities, marketing and partnership networks are needed which are expected to create social impacts such as job creation, increasing community income and social cohesion and inclusive economic growth.

In previous research Riezki [12], stated that one of the strategies for dealing with poverty is to increase people's income through empowerment programs. Pachorkar et al. [13], states that one of the poverty alleviation strategies is through the social entrepreneurship program, because it has the ability to create new jobs. Tanchangya et al.[14] stated that social entrepreneurship has the ability to affect the surrounding community by changing behavior in doing business and having an impact on improving the surrounding environment. Hussain et al. [15]stated that social entrepreneurship programs contribute to women's empowerment for poverty assuagement, likewise they have the ability to increase social innovation and change people's behaviour in social activities.

The same thing was also dispatched by Yanti and Adi [16] stating that PKH is one strategy to accelerate income generation through the creation of businesses to empower beneficiary families in mentoring programs. Djafar et al. [17] stated that poverty assuagement strategies based on community empowerment programs are accomplished through activities, assistance, facilitation, and promotion based on the 5C principles (communicating, coordinating, collaborating, and cooperating based on the consciousness).

Based on the reasons stated above, this research will analyse the governance of the social entrepreneurship program. The analysis is undertaken through the planning approach of initial business formation, pre-production, production process, and post-production in supporting the success of the program.

II. METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach that provides a comprehensive perspective and in-depth understanding of a social phenomenon being studied. Bryman [18] states that qualitative research uses more explanations in the form of descriptions of words, as well as qualitative research is interpretive by making an interpretation of what is seen, heard and understood [19]. A qualitative approach was chosen with the aim of building an understanding of the phenomenon of social entrepreneurship [20]. The type of research is determined based on the benefits of research, research objectives, dimensions of research time and data collection techniques. Based on the research objectives, this type of research is explanatory to investigate the causes of a social phenomenon[20].

Based on data collection techniques, this research uses qualitative data collection techniques. The data collected is in the form of words, sentences, and pictures. In qualitative data collection techniques, field research is performed, particularly direct observation through observation, recording notes and interviews with research subjects in a natural way at a certain time span [21].

The location of data collection in this research was completed in DKI Jakarta Province, with the consideration that DKI Jakarta Province is one of the provinces that is deemed successful in community empowerment programs, particularly social entrepreneurship. Moreover, DKI Jakarta has been a pilot province

of the Ministry of Social Affairs in terms of empowering families who are beneficiaries of the Family Hope Program through social entrepreneurship in 2020. This program is acknowledged for empowering poor and vulnerable families to increase their income. Likewise, to empowering families, the DKI Jakarta Provincial Government is thoroughly successful in capacitating poor families through the Family Hope Program.

This research was conducted for 12 months from November 2020 to November 2021. In selecting informants, criteria, and framework for selecting informants were arranged, according to Kreuger and Neuman [21], the informant selection technique was based not only on the representation of the informants but also on the ability, depth of understanding of the social situation being premeditated and the needs of the research. Based on the selection criteria, the informants in this study consisted of KPM PKH who had certified who could explain the initial implementation process of the business on the occasion of they were still members of PKH to the social entrepreneurship program and had a business that could explain business governance, from planning, production processes to post-production.

In order to attain complete and in-depth data, data collection was accomplished through observation, in-depth interviews and documentation research. Data technique analysis is accomplished through sorting and classifying data, open coding, axial coding, selective coding, interpretation, and elaboration.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Poverty reduction policies are broadly directed at two strategies, such as the fulfillment of basic needs for decent living and social empowerment. The two strategies are implemented in harmony to ensure the target group receives sustainable activities in building self-reliance. One form of social empowerment is a social entrepreneurship program. Social entrepreneurship combines business and social perspectives in poverty reduction endeavors. This is in line with Ife [22] which reveals empowerment as *"an effort to increase the power of disadvantaged people over their personal choices and life; chances; definition of needs; ideas; institutions; resources; economic and reproductive activities by intervening through planning and policy making; political and social action; and education."*

The success of poverty reduction through social entrepreneurship programs in DKI Jakarta Province is influenced by four main governance processes, specifically the program planning process, pre-production, production, and post-production processes. In achieving this success target, the central government, local governments, business incubators and aides must play an active role in supporting the development of social entrepreneurship programs.

Figure 2. Governance of the Implementation of the Social Entrepreneurship Program
(Source: Research report data)

3.1 Business start-up planning

Planning for the initial establishment of a business is a process of mapping and analyzing problems in determining policy interventions for empowerment programs for KPM.

Figure 3. Business Start-up Planning (Source: Research report data).

In the planning process for the initial formation of a business, there are several steps that must be informed to the KPM of the social entrepreneurship program, starting from the first stage, such as the introduction of entrepreneurship, this stage is actualized through socialization by business assistants and mentors. The introduction of entrepreneurship is expected to provide information to KPM that the purpose of the social entrepreneurship program is to empower the poor and vulnerable who combine business and social activities in preventing and overcoming social risks. This is in line with Ife [22] which states that the role of the aide is to deliver information.

In the socialization stage, KPM is also given motivation to foster an entrepreneurial spirit which includes social values, civil society, innovation, and economic activity. This was expressed by Mrs. SK:

“Social value is the most distinctive element in social entrepreneurship to create social benefits for the community and the surrounding environment. Social entrepreneurship is an increase of one level from ordinary entrepreneurship which generally only aims at profit” (SK, Ministry of Social Affairs, 2021).

The second stage is the business formation scheme. In this stage, the needs and entrepreneurial potential of program recipients will be mapped as the basis for developing social entrepreneurship. Mapping of business needs is based on the expertise, skills, type of business, business network, business legality, and infrastructure owned by the beneficiaries, thus, business assistants and mentors have the ability to identify competency development needs according to their expertise.

One of the crucial steps in social entrepreneurship is the identification of opportunities. Lumpkin et al. [23] stated that a business or social entrepreneurship activity cannot be accomplished haphazardly and without good planning. This type of business mapping likewise analyzes business needs from capital, resources, and sales value as well as digs deeper into the factors that affect the business, hence, the market for the production of this type of business can be developed.

The third stage is the initial business capital financing system. At this stage, the sources and needs of venture capital will be analyzed to facilitate KPM in accessing business financing. The results showed that the initial business financing was sourced from the allowance for PKH assistance received and initial business capital loans from the closest family. Access to capital through financial institutions is experiencing obstacles given the low ability of KPM to complete loan administration needs and concerns over the potential risk of default. This was delivered by Mrs. IJ, a seller of *Nasi Uduk* in the area of Penggilingan Suburb, Cakung District, East Jakarta City:

“The inceptive funds for the business come from the accoutrement of PKH assistance and a small loan from colleagues, this fund is used to buy raw materials. I have not dared to borrow through the bank for fear of not being able to repay it. The inceptive funds are not too big to sell Nasi Uduk, hence it is enough to take advantage of savings and loans from friends” (IJ, 2021).

The inadequate qualification to complete administrative needs is related to the irregularity of KPM in accomplishing business records. Generally, financial records have not been considered by KPM. There needs to

be an incitement for KPM to record financial transactions, at least a systematic report of financial position and profit and loss can be accessible hence it can provide information on the position of assets, liabilities/loans, profit gains, sales turnover and thus it has the ability to be used for loan application requirements financial institutions. This is in line with the statement of Chirinko and Singha[24] that an entrepreneur needs to understand the preparation of financial plans and cash flow management hence the business he runs can run well, be planned, and reduce the risk of business failure.

The fourth stage is determining the type of business, at this stage the Ministry of Social Affairs, Social Service, Mentors and Social Assistance will provide advice and considerations to KPM in determining the type of business chosen. This is in line with Mayo in Adi[25] that the skills that should be mastered to support the roles of a community worker are: relationship building skills, assessment skills, research skills, etc. These suggestions and considerations are not binding for KPM to be followed. The decision to determine the type of business remains the right of the KPM, either following the advice and considerations of the aide or mentor, as well as the closest family. This was delivered by Mrs. TS, a *Kue Basah* seller and Mrs. PS, a seller of planting media.

“The idea for this Bugis cake business came from the family, due to the reason that the majority of the surrounding population are Bugis residents. Moreover, there is a high demand from residents for event needs”(TS, 2021).

“At first, my business was a doughnut food business, but it did not develop well, after this mentor, I was advised to a planting media business, and Alhamdulillah my planting media business has grown, and I have the ability to have employees and have the ability to rent a pick-up car for planting media distribution to existing customers” (PS, 2021).

The fifth stage is initial business training, at this stage, the advisers or mentors will analyze the results of interviews with KPM to determine the type of initial business training needed. The results showed that the initial business training for KPM includes financial management, digital marketing and effective business management. This initial training has an impact on business development and expansion of marketing reach. Therefore, in the initial business planning process, there needs to be training for KPM, as informed by informants from Kebayoran Baru Suburb, Kebayoran Baru District, South Jakarta:

“I am very grateful for the guidance of this social entrepreneurship business mentor, at first I could not and did not understand good bookkeeping, hence I did not know how to set aside profits for savings and how to calculate cost of goods sold and how to record good, with this training I have the ability to monitor the progress of my business and eventually Alhamdulillah I have the ability to open a branch again”(TT, KPM, 2021).

This analysis is strengthened by Ife [22] that training is the most specific and fundamental educational role focused on learning a particular topic. Training can be interpreted as a planned process to modify attitudes or behaviour toward knowledge, and skills through learning experiences.

3.2 Pre-Production

The pre-production stage of the social entrepreneurship program will identify several needs that affect the development of the KPM business, such as the need for human resources and the production of raw materials. Based on data from the Social Service, DKI Jakarta Province 2021, human resources are dominated by workers who come from their own families.

Table 1. Human Resources and Social Entrepreneurship in DKI Jakarta Province

Human Resources/Cities	Central Jakarta	West Jakarta	East Jakarta	South Jakarta	North Jakarta
Alone	2	5	6	4	29
Family help	4	6	8	22	9
Have employees		1	1	2	7

Source: Social Service, DKI Jakarta Province, 2021.

Based on the table above, human resources in social entrepreneurship programs in DKI Jakarta Province are dominated by their own workers or workers who come from their own families. In certain cases, there are several KPM businesses that have involved workers outside their own families. Generally, the involvement of workers from outside the family is a KPM business that already has more than one branch or a business that has developed, as an informant from Kebayoran Baru in South Jakarta said:

“Alhamdulillah, this Martabak business already employs 6 people with the help of 3 people from the family, thus, are 9 people in total. Along with this additional workforce, they are favorable in business development, the income of this Martabak business has increased, hence we have the ability to add several branches in the South Jakarta area” (TH, KPM, 2021).

Based on these findings, it can be analyzed that the addition of human resources in the implementation of production needs to be considered, to accelerate production, the impact of which can increase business development. According to Aude de Montesquieu et al. (2014) that in planning for business improvement, business entities need to increase the scale of the program, notably in terms of human and financial resources. Similarly, Carmeli and Schaubroeck [26] concede that human resources that are valuable, unique, and not easily replaced have a strong correlation with organizational performance.

Other needs are related to the availability of raw materials as a need that needs to be considered in the implementation of the business. Social entrepreneurship KPM is generally easy to meet business raw material needs, due to the reason of the ease in accessing raw material suppliers. The challenge in the supply of raw materials is more on the increase in the price of raw materials which causes a decrease in operating profits. Several KPMs have worked around this by storing raw materials in sufficient quantities for several times of production, as stated by informants from Kapuk Muara Suburb, North Jakarta and Tebet Suburb, South Jakarta:

“From the profit I got, I buy raw materials repeatedly, thus, there is a stock of raw materials, in order to buy them I buy them at an agent who I have enlisted” (TS, 2021).

“In order to buy bag products, we buy them at a bag agent in Pasar Senen, we buy them every day when there is demand and the products run out” (NR, 2021).

3.3 Production

The implementation of the production process includes business training and division of labour duties according to their expertise. The training at the production stage was organized by TKSK assistants, business mentors and the DKI Jakarta Provincial Social Service. First, training in supporting production includes increasing business motivation, efficient management of raw materials, environmental responsibility related to production waste management, increasing product competence, and financial records, as one informant stated:

“Mr. David (mentor) provided socialization on good selling methods, such as paying attention to food hygiene and the use of safe raw materials. Mr. David likewise gave training to me on how to properly dispose of used cooking oil and how to dispose of plastic hence it is not disposed of carelessly” (TH, KPM, Kebayoran Baru, 2021).

From these findings, it can be analyzed that training is important to improve the ability and expertise of KPM in social entrepreneurship programs. Ife [22] states that training will be more effective in the event that the skills taught are skills needed by the community. In this case, the community is involved to determine the type of training needed.

Second, the scheme of division of tasks according to their respective expertise. Based on the results of the study, it was found that KPM social entrepreneurship still does not have production specialization in accordance with the division of tasks. KPM PKH still relies on assisted workers from families, thus there is no expertise and specialization in production work, for that in improving quality and quality, mentors are needed to support guidance regarding the importance of specialization in supporting KPM business development. The same opinion was delivered by one of the informants of a *Martabak* seller located in Kebayoran Baru, South Jakarta:

“Specialization is important, in order to maintain the quality and taste of Martabak, as well as in marketing expertise, there is 1 (one) employee who only accepts orders from Gojek or Shopee food, thus focus on service”(TH, KPM, 2021).

Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that specialization in the implementation of production is one of the most influential factors in accelerating business production. Moreover, standardization in social entrepreneurship needs to be improved in order to improve the quality and quality of production. This is supported by the results of research[27], that task specialization is prepared based on job descriptions by answering questions in regard to the component, characteristics, education, experience, and others of the person who will accomplish the job well.

3.4 Post-Production

In the development and marketing of social entrepreneurship products, there are several factors that have the ability to influence it, such as product marketing methods, business licensing, technology utilization, and product packaging.

Figure 4. Business Development and Marketing (Source: Research report data).

The first is the product marketing method, the marketing method for the production of 109 KPM in DKI Jakarta province is divided based on the type of business. The marketing method used by KPM social entrepreneurship is still dominated in the area where KPM lives. For retail and grocery businesses, marketing is generally done by opening kiosks or stalls, while for culinary businesses and several other types of services, the marketing method is "door to door" around KPM's residence.

Figure 5. Social Entrepreneurship Program Marketing Networks in DKI Jakarta Province (Source: Ministry of Social Affairs, 2021).

Based on Figure 5 above, in retail and grocery businesses, the marketing method is done by opening a kiosk or stall, while for culinary businesses and several other types of services, marketing methods are accomplished by going to houses around KPM or in other places. Likewise with the selling point system accomplished by KPM by entrusting its business products to kiosks or stalls. There are several culinary businesses and street vendors of bag production selling on street and selling on carts.

Marketing development needs to be developed through the use of social media networks and marketplaces, utilizing partnerships, and involving KPM in numerous bazaars or exhibitions with a social perspective. Kotler [28] states that the concept of socially oriented marketing is a concept that seeks to meet the needs of consumers' desires and interests thus they have the ability to meet consumer satisfaction efficiently and effectively and make people's lives better.

Second, for business licenses, all KPMs that are given social entrepreneurship assistance in DKI Jakarta Province already have a Business Identification Number (NIB) and a Micro and Small Business License (IUMK). Regarding distribution permits such as PIRT, BPOM and halal, not many have received permits due to the strict requirements to attain such permits, as information from business mentors:

“In order to attain a PIRT permit, KPM must follow and have a certificate of food safety counselling, moreover, to pass the inspection test for food product testing facilities, and comply with the food labelling legislation” (DV, Mentor, 2021).

KPM hopes to be assisted in licensing PIRT, BPOM and halal, due to the fact that with this distribution permit it has the ability to join up with convenience stores and supermarkets. Moreover, to this permit, it is favorable in building buyers' trust in the quality and feasibility of the product, as was the informant who delivered about the application for the Halal and PIRT label management.

“...in terms of business licensing I already have an NIB and IUMK but for halal and PIRT permits it is still in process, I hope that the Government can help in the issuance of this permit” (TS, Jakarta Utara, 2021).

Third, the use of technology, the use of technology by KPM in marketing product products is accomplished through social media, marketplaces and other online marketing promotion networks. KPM utilizes social media as a marketing medium, because of its easy access and affordable costs. In general, KPM uses Facebook and WhatsApp accounts in marketing their products. Several KPMs were found to have used the available marketplaces such as Shopee, Tokopedia, Bukalapak as well as through go-send and go-jek services.

The use of technology in the marketing process has proven to be very helpful in increasing sales, improving product quality, and encouraging KPM to improve the quality of product photos through product photography technique training. According to Zastrow in Adi [29] the basic components that must be considered and elaborated on in developing the practitioner profession in the field of social work and social welfare, one which is skills, it is a crucial thing in providing assistance and is a prerequisite if the profession wants to develop.

Fourth is product packaging, product packaging techniques marketed by KPM have received guidance from assistants and mentors, particularly for food and culinary products, almost all of which have been packaged in a well-kept and pleasant form. KPM Social Entrepreneurship in DKI Jakarta, thus far they have not received training on how a product can be packaged properly, but numerous small entrepreneurs have started implementing branding and packaging strategies.

As stated by Kotler and Armstrong[30] packaging is defined as the act of wrapping or closing an item or set of goods with packaging material. The packaging material can be paper, glass and others. Packaging management is a coordinated system to make goods ready to be transported and distributed to users. Packaging likewise plays an important role in food supply chain management, the need to reduce costs, reduce environmental impacts, and e-commerce [31].

IV. CONCLUSION

Social entrepreneurship programs have become a strategy used by numerous countries to reduce poverty through increased income. In the context of Indonesia, social entrepreneurship programs are used as empowerment policy interventions to optimize community participation in achieving sustainable social welfare improvements based on four values, such as social values, civil society, innovation, and economic activity. In order to provide a more complete picture of the success of social entrepreneurship programs in poverty assuagement, this research tries to contribute to the literature related to the analysis of social entrepreneurship program governance. In general, there are four main processes that influence the success of social entrepreneurship programs, such as initial business planning, pre-production, production processes, and post-production.

In the planning process of starting a business, social entrepreneurship programs are emphasized as empowerment that combines business and social activities in preventing and overcoming social risks and problems. The initial business planning stage includes a business establishment scheme that maps the entrepreneurial needs and potential of program recipients as the basis for developing social entrepreneurship and determining the type of business. Mapping of business needs is based on the expertise, skills, type of business, business network, business legality, capital needs, and infrastructure owned by the beneficiaries, to identify the need for competency development in accordance with the expertise possessed.

The pre-production process of the social entrepreneurship program identifies the needs that affect the KPM business, such as the need for human resources and the production of raw materials. Generally, human resources or labour in the production of social entrepreneurship are accomplished by workers who come from their own families and the surrounding community. The involvement of the surrounding community is one of the efforts to increase the role of the community in empowerment so that it has a positive impact on improving skills and economic growth. Availability of production raw materials is likewise a requirement that is considered in the implementation of the business. Generally, beneficiaries have direct access to suppliers to ensure the availability of goods and the stability of raw material prices.

The production process includes training and division of tasks that support the business. The training provided in the production stage includes increasing business motivation, efficient management of raw materials, environmental responsibility, increasing product competence, and financial records, including business management in managing the division of tasks. In general, beneficiaries still rely on assisted labour from families, thus expertise and specialization in production work have not yet been formed. The role of the aide supports awareness of specialization in the division of tasks, considering that specialization in the implementation of production is one of the most influential factors in accelerating business production, and improving product quality and quality.

The post-production process is the development and marketing of social entrepreneurship products. In the post-production stage, emphasis is placed on marketing methods, licensing, technology utilization, and product packaging. Marketing development is not only accomplished in the surrounding area but has been developed through the use of technology, social media networks, marketplaces, the use of partnerships that have

an impact on business development. Beneficiaries recognize the importance of product packaging and licensing in building buyer tenacity in product quality and viability. The social entrepreneurship program has exhilarated all beneficiaries to have business licenses, expertise in packaging, and their own brands.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Govender, N. Kamaran, N. Patchett, A. Ruddle, G. Torr, and N. Van Zyl, "Poverty and inequality in South Africa and the world," *South African Actuar. J.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 117–160, 2007.
- [2] T. C. Leasiwal, "Determinan dan Karakteristik Kemiskinan di Provinsi Maluku," *Cita Ekon.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1–26, 2013.
- [3] H. Habibullah, "Perlindungan Sosial Komprehensif di Indonesia," *Sosio Inf.*, vol. 3, no. 1, 2017.
- [4] ADB, "ADB and Social Protection: Challenges and Opportunities," 2011.
- [5] D. Budlender, "Conditional cash transfers: Learning from the literature," *UNICEF UN Women, Caribb.*, 2014.
- [6] N. Cahyadi, R. Hanna, B. A. Olken, R. A. Prima, E. Satriawan, and E. Syamsulhakim, "Cumulative impacts of conditional cash transfer programs: Experimental evidence from Indonesia," *Am. Econ. J. Econ. Policy*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 88–110, 2020.
- [7] A. McCord, "Linking Social Protection to Sustainable Employment: Current Practices and Future Directions. Social Protection for Employment Community (SPEC)." 2018.
- [8] M. Payne, "Modern Social Work Theory (4. bs.)," *Engl. Palgrave Macmillan*, 2014.
- [9] L. Hulgård, "Discourses of social entrepreneurship—Variations of the same theme," *EMES Eur. Res. Netw.*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 2–21, 2010.
- [10] F. Perrini and C. Vurro, "Social entrepreneurship: Innovation and social change across theory and practice," in *Social entrepreneurship*, Springer, 2006, pp. 57–85.
- [11] J. Austin, H. Stevenson, and J. Wei-Skillern, "Social and commercial entrepreneurship: same, different, or both?," *Entrep. theory Pract.*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 1–22, 2006.
- [12] D. R. Pratama, "Peran Kewirausahaan Sosial dalam Pemberdayaan Masyarakat: Tiga Cerita dari Kutai Timur," *Umbara*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 115–129, 2019.
- [13] S. Pachorkar, S. Kawishwar, and P. Sharda, "Women entrepreneurship and women empowerment in India: A case study of Jwala Mahila Samiti," *Prest. Int. J. Manag. Res.*, vol. 12, pp. 254–264, 2020.
- [14] P. Tanchangya, C. Yingjing, and N. H. Chowdhury, "Social entrepreneurs role on poverty reduction through job creation," *North Am. Acad. Res.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 420–438, 2020.
- [15] M. D. Hussain, A. B. Bhuiyan, and R. Bakar, "Entrepreneurship development and poverty alleviation: An empirical review," *J. Asian Sci. Res.*, vol. 4, no. 10, pp. 558–573, 2014.
- [16] D. F. Yanti and I. R. Adi, "Analisis Process Terhadap Strategi Graduasi Keluarga Penerima Manfaat Program Keluarga Harapan Di Kabupaten Cianjur Dalam Kerangka Result-Based Management," *EMPATI J. Ilmu Kesejaht. Sos.*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 146–163, 2021.
- [17] R. Djafar, H. Syam, P. Raharjo, J. Abdussamad, and H. Akib, "Reconstruction of poverty reduction strategy model based on community empowerment programs," *Acad. Entrep. J.*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 1–10, 2019.
- [18] A. Bryman, "Social research methods 3rd edition." Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008.
- [19] J. W. Creswell and J. D. Creswell, *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications, 2017.
- [20] M. Alston and W. Bowles, "Research for Social Workers: Introduction for Methods and Practice." London, Taylor and Francis, 2003.
- [21] L. Kreuger and W. L. Neuman, *Social work research methods: qualitative and quantitative approaches: with Research Navigator*. Pearson/Allyn and Bacon, 2006.
- [22] J. Ife, *Community development in an uncertain world*. Cambridge University Press, 2013.
- [23] G. T. Lumpkin, T. W. Moss, D. M. Gras, S. Kato, and A. S. Amezcua, "Entrepreneurial processes in social contexts: how are they different, if at all?," *Small Bus. Econ.*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 761–783, 2013.
- [24] R. S. Chirinko and A. R. Singha, "Testing static tradeoff against pecking order models of capital structure: a critical comment," *J. financ. econ.*, vol. 58, no. 3, pp. 417–425, 2000.
- [25] I. R. Adi, *Kesejahteraan Sosial*. PT RajaGrafindo Persada, 2013.
- [26] A. Carmeli and J. Schaubroeck, "How leveraging human resource capital with its competitive distinctiveness enhances the performance of commercial and public organizations," *Hum. Resour. Manag. Publ. Coop. with Sch. Bus. Adm. Univ. Michigan Alliance with Soc. Hum. Resour. Manag.*, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 391–412, 2005.
- [27] M. S. P. Hasibuan, "Manajemen sumber daya manusia." Bumi Aksara, Jakarta, 2001.
- [28] P. Kotler, "Manajemen pemasaran: analisis, perencanaan, implementasi, dan kontrol," *Jakarta: Prenhallindo*, 1997.
- [29] I. R. Adi, "Intervensi Komunitas dan Pengembangan Masyarakat: Sebagai Upaya Pemberdayaan Masyarakat," *PT RajaGrafindo Persada Jakarta*, 2013.
- [30] P. Kotler and G. Armstrong, "Prinsip-prinsip pemasaran jilid 1 edisi 12," *Jakarta: Erlangga*, 2008.
- [31] A. Regattieri, G. Santarelli, M. Gamberi, and C. Mora, "A new paradigm for packaging design in web-based commerce," *Int. J. Eng. Bus. Manag.*, vol. 6, no. Godište 2014, pp. 6–14, 2014.